

THE UNIVERSITY of EDINBURGH
Centre for Data, Culture & Society

CDCS **ANNUAL** **REPORT**

2023-2024

2023-2024

FIVE YEARS OF DATA, CULTURE & SOCIETY

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HELLO!

WHAT A DIFFERENCE A YEAR MAKES! AS WE CELEBRATE THE FIFTH ANNIVERSARY OF THE CENTRE FOR DATA, CULTURE & SOCIETY, WE FIND OURSELVES IN A NEW OFFICE WITH NEW COLLEAGUES, SEEING NEW HORIZONS OPENING BEFORE US.

This report presents our accomplishments over the academic year 23/24, setting out the ways in which we have collaborated with and supported digital research communities in the arts, humanities and social sciences in Edinburgh and beyond. It also shows how we are beginning to work more collaboratively within our new home, the Edinburgh Futures Institute, as we begin to scale up the support we offer to build even greater capacity for data-led research.

This year has seen the team explore new formats for skills development, begin to establish new services and consolidate our relationships across the College. Highlights have included supporting the University's Students as Change Agents programme; becoming part of the UK's DARIAH community; hosting the Digital Humanities Research Software Engineering Summer School in partnership with King's Digital Lab, Cambridge Digital Humanities and the Alan Turing Institute; planning our annual lecture, this year given by artist and scholar Mary Flanagan; and, of course, congratulating winners of the CDCS Digital Research Prizes at our ceremony in June. You can read all about these activities and more in the pages that follow.

During the refurbishment of the old Royal Infirmary into what is now EFI's new home, a group of creative makers collaborated with local communities to build 'The Spirit Case', an object that honours the transition of the building into a new kind of public space. Assembled out of memories and materials from the building and grounds, it is a symbol of both transition and EFI's ambition to remain a place of care, compassion, openness and accessibility. Passing the Spirit Case every day in our new building, at a time of transition for the Centre, it is inspiring to imagine how we, too, are in an ongoing process of renewal. We hope that the work in this report represents not only the original spirit of CDCS but also the foundations from which we will grow and develop in the coming years.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

This report reflects the activities of a brilliant, dedicated and hardworking team. Lucia Michielin continues to lead a fantastic training programme, along with her merry band of Training Fellows; Likando Kumoyo brings her design skills and detail-oriented planning to our events and training, ensuring that everything comes together perfectly on the day; and Ed MacKenzie shares his developer skills with our research community, providing expert assistance across many varied projects.

This year, we also benefitted from the support of Laura Murray and Megan Morris. Laura was our administrative assistant until the spring, when she moved on to a new role in Moray House, and Megan, our Summer School Coordinator, went on to submit her Masters thesis at the end of summer. We wish Laura and Megan the best as they move forward with their careers.

Sincere thanks go to Dr Robin Hill, Chair of the CDCS Advisory Board throughout 2023/24. His active leadership of the board and his supportive involvement with the Centre's activities was greatly appreciated. Likewise, thanks are due to all our Advisory Board members whose insights and perspectives are crucial in shaping our work and the support we provide to the CAHSS research community.

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Director

CDCS PEOPLE

LISA OTTY
DIRECTOR

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Digital Research Skills
Training Manager

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WENLONG LI
Senior Researcher, Bytedance, Privacy
and Data Protection Office

EVENTS

SOMETHING FOR EVERYONE

Alongside a rich mix of works in progress, project deep dives and networking events, this year we were delighted to introduce a new 'masterclass' format into our events programme. Our masterclasses invite digital methods experts from around the world to share their expertise with our researchers. We continue to offer both in-person and live-streamed seminars, although attendance for online events has dropped significantly from a peak during the pandemic. As people increasingly return to campus more regularly, however, we've been pleased to see the number of attendees at in-person events like our fikas and socials growing again. It's wonderful to be able to meet face to face and forge strong bonds with members of our local digital research community.

HOW TO SEE WHAT'S MISSING

Mary Flanagan

This year, designer and researcher Mary Flanagan took us on a journey through her creative practices and explored what it means to be a hyperdisciplinary feminist artist in the age of machine learning and artificial intelligence. Mary is the Sherman Fairchild Distinguished Professor of Digital

Humanities at Dartmouth College and leader of the design research laboratory Tiltfactor.org. Her work uses image-making feminist AI to think critically about the thorny biases behind technological learning systems and artworks.

COLLABORATIVE EVENTS

(WHEN) DOES CIVIC EDUCATION WORK? EVIDENCE FROM A CROSS-NATIONAL ONLINE EXPERIMENT (WITH AYKUT ÖZTÜRK, STEVEN FINKEL, AND ERICKA RASCON RAMIREZ)

CDCS hosted Anja Neundorf, University of Glasgow, in partnership with the Social Data Science Hub.

UNDERSTANDING LEARNING IN THE WORLD OF AI

We partnered with the Centre for Technomoral Futures to host a talk by David William Schaffer from the University of Wisconsin-Madison.

DATA ACCESS AND RESEARCH FOR SOCIAL BENEFIT: MOVING FORWARD

We partnered with the British Academy to deliver a workshop focused on data access and its implications for research and policy.

MASTERCLASSES

TURN YOUR GRAPHS INTO INTERACTIVE ONLINE EXPERIENCES: PYTHON SHINY APPS FOR BEGINNERS

Pawel Orzechowski, University of Edinburgh.

CREATING DEEP CONVOLUTIONAL NEURAL NETWORKS FOR IMAGE CLASSIFICATION

Nabeel Siddiqui, Susquehanna University. In partnership with Programming Historian.

KEYPHRASE NETWORK ANALYSIS

Pedro Jacobetty, University of Potsdam.

MASTERCLASS IMAGE AND TEXT ANALYSIS USING MULTI-MODAL EMBEDDINGS

Justin Chun-ting Ho, Amsterdam School of Communication Research.

COMPUTER VISION FOR THE HUMANITIES AND SOCIAL SCIENCES: AN INTRODUCTION TO DEEP LEARNING FOR IMAGE CLASSIFICATION

Daniel van Strien, Hugging Face. In partnership with Programming Historian.

EPISTEMIC NETWORK ANALYSIS

David Williamson Shaffer, University of Wisconsin-Madison.

SEMINAR SERIES

Towards a Prosopography of Musicians in Pre-Reformation Scotland: Adventures in Machine Learning and Digital Humanities

James Cook

PaleoVisions of Chauvet Cave: Virtual Reality at the Intersection of Art, Anthropology, and Digital Humanities

Nathaniel Dominy

Ecologies of Creation: 'Digital Repatriation' and their Afterlives

Arkotong Longkumer

Image and Text Analysis using Multi-modal Embeddings

Justin Chun-ting Ho

(When) Does Civic Education Work? Evidence from a Cross-National Online Experiment (with Aykut Öztürk, Steven Finkel, and Ericka Rascon Ramirez)

Anja Neundorf

Fairness by Design: Empowering Children Interacting with Educational AI

Ayça Atabey

Digitization for Social Welfare: Examining the Building and Other Construction Workers' (BOCW) Welfare Funds in India

Sruthi Herbert

'Who is /ourguy/?': Tracing Memes to Study Online Subcultures

Sal Hagen

Understanding Learning in the World of AI

David Williamson Shaffer

Alternative Canons: Topic Modelling Fanfiction Reviews on Goodreads.com

Suzanne Black

Imagining AI: Computing Stories in a Museum Context

Ursula Martin

FIKAS & SOCIALS

Providing opportunities for researchers to connect is an important part of our work at the Centre. Digital research is often interdisciplinary, and it can be hard to meet those working with the same methods in other disciplines. To help, we hold regular informal get-togethers or meetings with no agendas, at which conversation and coffee flow freely; these 'fikas' are always popular, and we encourage anyone with an interest in digital research to come along.

REGISTRATIONS BY COUNTRY

- 1-5 REGISTRATIONS BY COUNTRY
- 50-100 REGISTRATIONS BY COUNTRY
- 100+ REGISTRATIONS BY COUNTRY

REGISTRATIONS BY CONTINENT

"GREAT! INTERESTING! LIVELY!"
"MARY FLAGAN'S LECTURE AND Q&A WAS FANTASTIC, THANK YOU FOR ORGANISING."
 ANNUAL LECTURE ATTENDEE

TRAINING

BUILDING DATA SKILLS.

Our digital research methods training programme continued at pace this year, serving more researchers than ever: for the first time, we recorded more than 1,000 sign-ups over our 62 courses. Reflecting the brilliant diversity of our research community, we offered courses on subjects ranging from topic modelling, to statistics, to photogrammetry. Our talented team of Training Fellows also helped us to deliver another CDCS Summer School, this year with two streams and over 40 attendees. We've also improved the accessibility of our online materials with a new GitHub interface, work that we will continue to build on in the coming year.

CDCS TRAINING COURSES: 62

CDCS TRAINING REGISTRATIONS: 1003

TRAINING PROGRAMME

Demand for CDCS training opportunities grows year after year, with 1,003 staff and students signing up for over 60 courses in academic year 23/24. Courses ranged from structured and unstructured data analysis, introduction to programming, GIS, to digital drawing and 3D data, and were designed and facilitated by our Training Fellows as well as colleagues from EDINA, Library, LLC, University Collections and uCreate Studio.

SHARING OUR MATERIALS

Since we created our GitHub page in 2021, our collection of materials has grown to 77 repositories contributed by 33 people. To encourage people to use these materials, we have developed a dedicated navigation page designed to offer a user-friendly interface that supports both title-based and thematic searches across our repositories. Additionally, we are actively curating a selection of self-contained tutorials on our GitHub, ensuring that users can easily find and engage with the content that best meets their needs.

OUR CORE TOPICS

Digitised documents & text analysis: training on the processes of working with unstructured data from the extraction of information from digitised documents to advance language models.

Intro to programming: introductory classes that help attendees to familiarise themselves with the main programming languages.

Data wrangling & data visualisation: training on the practicalities of exploring datasets from cleaning messy data to producing effective visualisations.

Structured data analysis: from descriptive statistics to regression and null-hypothesis testing.

Geographical data: training on working with spatial data from introducing GIS to bridging data analysis and geographical data.

Digital drawing & 3D data: from technical drawing in AutoCAD to acquiring, processing and printing 3D data.

Good practices of digital research: exploring the practicalities of doing digital research from working with pre-prints to data ethics.

CDCS TRAINING FELLOWS 23/24

AISLINN KEOGH

Aislinn is a PhD student in the Centre for Language Evolution. Her research combines behavioural experiments and agent-based modelling to investigate the role of language production biases in the emergence of linguistic structure. She is proficient in Python, R and JavaScript and is passionate about the use of simulation-based techniques for experimental design and data analysis.

BRIAN TSZ HO WONG

Brian Tsz Ho Wong is a PhD candidate (East Asian Studies) in the School of Literatures, Languages & Cultures. His research explores the networks of capital and power elites in the wartime Japanese Empire, and the use of private capital to fuel imperial ambitions. He is passionate about using digital tools (Gephi, QGIS and Google Earth) in his research. At CDGS, he is excited to teach and support the use of Gephi in humanities and interdisciplinary studies.

CHRIS OLDNALL

Chris is a PhD mathematics researcher with the MAC-MIGS Centre of Doctoral Training, who is affiliated with the Institute of Genetics and Cancer. His work is interdisciplinary and involves combining causal inference with genomics. He loves teaching individuals on how to get the most out of 'big data' by using data analysis techniques appropriately and accurately, and most importantly how to implement these in Python and R.

BHARGAVI GANESH

Bhargavi is a PhD student doing interdisciplinary research at the intersection of philosophy, computer science, and public policy. She is affiliated with the Center for Technomoral Futures and the UKRI Research Node on Trustworthy Autonomous Systems Governance and Regulation. She has worked at non-profit research organizations and government institutions, where she studied the impact of housing policies on marginalized groups. In her doctoral research, Bhargavi is developing frameworks to guide the governance and regulation of autonomous systems and decision-making algorithms in various fields including health, robotics, and finance.

SARAH VAN EYNDHOVEN

Sarah van Eyndhoven is based within the school of Philosophy, Psychology and Language Sciences, where she has recently finished her PhD in historical sociolinguistics. Her project explored the use of Scots language features in eighteenth century Scottish correspondence, sourced from the National Library of Scotland. Combining Handwritten Text Recognition models to automatically transcribe a large collection of written letters, with corpus software and statistical modelling, Sarah was able to uncover the influence of different social and political factors in predicting Scots usage in an underexplored area of historical Scots scholarship.

FANG JACKSON-YANG

Fang is a PhD student at the School of Philosophy, Psychology, and Language Sciences. Her project investigates how speakers encode prominent information in simulated conversations and how listeners predict upcoming utterances in comprehension. She works with both laboratory and corpus data. She conducts data analyses in R using multivariate statistical tools such as mixed-effects models.

JAMES BESSE

James is a PhD student in Science, Technology and Innovation Studies. His research concerns the implementation of e-ID systems, specifically looking at the EU Settlement Scheme. He uses text mining alongside social surveys and interviews to understand user experience with the EUSS.

KI TONG

Ki is a PhD candidate at the Advanced Care Research Centre studying ways to enhance greenspace accessibility for older adults. She is a landscape architect with professional experience delivering construction projects and landscape assessments. Besides an interest in using QGIS and ArcGIS for geospatial visualisation and analysis, she expanded her exploration with aggregating geospatial data and performing further analysis with R to study the correlation between environmental variables and urban density.

MARTIN DISLEY

Martin Disley is a practice-led design researcher based at the Institute for Design Informatics at the University of Edinburgh. His critical engineering studio practice blends artistic inquiry and investigative computing, producing outputs in software, film, installation, and text. His PhD research explores adversarial design and investigative aesthetics as Research through Design methods for explainability and interpretability of generative computer vision. Prior to pursuing his PhD, he worked as a software developer for a music technology startup and as a research engineer at the University of Edinburgh.

XAN COCHRAN

Xan Cochran (they/them) is a Research Masters' student in Informatics, with supervisors in Informatics and Philosophy. Their research concerns the metaphysics of 'levels' in scientific discourses, and combines philosophical analysis with the computational modelling of epistemic communities. They hold degrees in English Literature and Developmental Linguistics, and have for the last decade been working as a tutor for the University, having tutored in the Schools of Informatics; Philosophy, Psychology, and Language Sciences; Social and Political Sciences; Biological Sciences; Design; Music; Physics and Astronomy; Mathematics; Economics; and Geosciences. In their spare moments, they paint and write science fiction.

RHYS DAVIES

Rhys is based at the School of Health in Social Sciences. Rhys is a psychologist researching adaptive behaviours and mental health in elite sports. His research makes use of statistical modelling with survey data, particularly investigating interactions to determine how context shapes the efficacy of "adaptive" behaviours. His preferred coding language is R, and he is passionate about using data visualisation techniques to communicate and simplify research findings.

SARAH SCHÖTTLER

Sarah Schöttler is a PhD candidate at the VisHub lab in the School of Informatics. Her research explores responsive visualization with a focus on geographic data and visualization. She is active in the visualization community and has previously worked as a visualisation and map developer for clients such as the PeaceRep consortium at the Edinburgh Law School. At CDGS, she is excited to teach and offer support with data visualization and mapping, web development, and general programming skills.

"THIS WAS A CLEAR, LUCID AND BRILLIANTLY TAUGHT INTRODUCTION. AS A COMPLETE NOVICE TO GITHUB, I WAS RELIEVED THAT THE COURSE STARTED FROM THE ABSOLUTE BASICS, INTRODUCED EACH CONCEPT AND USE CLEARLY, AND ENABLED ME TO TRY OUT USING GITHUB MYSELF FOR A COUPLE OF VERY SIMPLE VERSION CONTROL PROCESSES. THE TEACHING WAS REALLY EXCELLENT, BOTH IN TERMS OF FORMAL PRESENTATION AND LESS FORMAL INDIVIDUAL HELP WITH PROBLEMS WHEN THEY AROSE."

PARTICIPANT \ TRAINING PROGRAMME 2023-24

CDCS SUMMER SCHOOL 2024

In June, we hosted our ever-popular Summer School, in which two simultaneously run streams catered to researchers with different skill levels. The Gentle Introduction to Coding for Humanities and Social Sciences course was designed for complete beginners to coding and data analysis. Through lectures and exercises, attendees of this stream learnt how to code in Python, starting from core concepts such as variables and loops through to coding live data visualisations. By the end of the course, attendees understood how to bridge the gap between humans and computers, and how to apply the skills they have learnt to their own data analysis and research.

The Data and Analysis in the Wild course was designed to help attendees with prior coding experience better understand how data and text analysis projects are performed in a research environment. Starting from identifying a series of research questions connected to this year's core topic, life in Scotland from the past to the present, attendees explored techniques for analysing a variety of real-world datasets. They learnt how computational methods can be used to obtain, clean and analyse structured and unstructured datasets in R to answer their research questions. Topics covered in this course included web scraping, text analysis, sentiment analysis, data wrangling, statistics and data visualisation.

"IT WAS ONE OF THE BEST WEEKS I HAVE HAD SINCE I STARTED MY PHD, AND HAS INSPIRED SO MANY IDEAS AND OPPORTUNITIES FOR MY OWN RESEARCH."

**PARTICIPANT **
CDCS SUMMER SCHOOL 2024

SKILLS

FLEXIBLE LEARNING MODELS

At CDCS, we believe that learning takes place inside and outside the classroom. Our skills activities supplement, enhance and expand our courses in flexible formats that enable self-paced study, learning-by-doing in real-world contexts, and integrating data and the digital within wider transferable skills development. By exploring how digital methodologies translate across topics, disciplines and departments, we aim to help researchers develop the skills required to collaborate effectively and conduct transdisciplinary data-led research. This year, we've worked with colleagues in the University Library, Careers Service and Data + Design Lab to support students and researchers as they tackle complex challenges.

SUPPORTING DATA SKILLS ACROSS THE UNIVERISTY**SACHA PROGRAMME**

Students as Change Agents (SACHA) is a challenge-based programme which brings together students from different subjects to solve real-world problems with a wider social, environmental, or economic impact. This year, we mentored the SACHA Data Coaches as they provided data support and computational methods development for students.

DATALAB ACADEMY

The Data Lab Academy's (TDLA) Innovation Week is a three-day programme aiming to equip Data Science students across Scotland with the tools and perspectives needed to co-design responses to complex challenges. This year, a CDCS data coach not only supported the attendees, but also helped transform the data provided by the industry-based partners into a user-friendly data playground.

DISSERTATION AND THESIS FESTIVAL

As part of the Dissertation and Thesis Festival, we organised a workshop focused on how students can use digital methods and library resources to derive new research insights. With a focus on text analysis, we explored out-of-the-box tools and more tailored solutions to analyse large bodies of text.

LEARNING THROUGH REAL WORLD CHALLENGES

It's common practice for trainers to use small, pre-cleaned and simplified data sets in courses and workshops. While working with clean data limits the cognitive load, it can lead to a disconnect with real-world data, making it difficult for learners to apply their learning to actual research projects.

We're interested in how we can support the connection between research and technical skills, and in how we can equip our researchers with the skills they'll need to work with real-world data in solving problems. We also aim to reuse and showcase the University's rich data collections.

Over the past year, we collaborated with colleagues from the Library to gather, process and prepare two of these collections for use in training and research. We focused primarily on the Statistical Account of Scotland and the Digitised PhD Theses datasets.

The Statistical Account of Scotland dataset comprises 29,083 text files derived from transcriptions of the Old and New Statistical Accounts of Scotland. The Digitised PhD Theses dataset includes metadata for approximately 25,000 PhD theses defended at the University of Edinburgh. We transformed both raw datasets into tabular formats, making them suitable for both teaching and research purposes. This dataset was used to teach Text Analysis at our Summer School and during training events across the year, enabling trainers to showcase a series of methods from data wrangling and data visualisation, to text analysis and topic modelling.

BURSARIES**ESSEX SUMMER SCHOOL IN SOCIAL SCIENCE DATA ANALYSIS**

This year, we sent Dr Johanna Amaya-Panche and Adam Farquhar of the PeaceRep project (Law) to the Essex Summer School in Social Science Data Analysis - 2J Machine Learning for Social Scientists and 3E Machine Learning for Tabular Data.

MSC IN SPEECH AND LANGUAGE PROCESSING

We continued supporting Professor Will Lamb (LLC) as he completed his course in Speech and Language Processing.

SUMMER INSTITUTE IN COMPUTATIONAL SOCIAL SCIENCES (SICSS)

This year, we helped Unai Gómez-Hernández (SSPS) to attend the Summer Institute in Computational Social Sciences.

SELF-PACED AND ONLINE LEARNING**TRAINING MATERIAL REPOSITORIES**

We now have over 77 repositories of CDCS training material in GitHub! You can navigate this collection and identify the right resources for your interests and skill level through our new training material navigation page, where we've stored self-contained tutorials. The navigation page is user-friendly and has a search function, making our GitHub more accessible.

ONLINE COURSES

Not all people learn the same way or have the same amount of time available, so we offer a diverse and flexible range of training opportunities. Our workshops and courses take place at varied times in a range of formats, some in person and some online. This year, we offered around 40% of our training online.

TRAINING PATHWAYS

Our training programme is designed to support researchers in the arts, humanities and social sciences. We offer six curated pathways for key methods, which can help you navigate online resources and tailor your skills development to your needs.

PROJECTS

SUPPORT FOR NEW IDEAS.

Sometimes, all it takes to get a project off the ground is a little help. This year, our team supported a wide variety of projects with guidance and advice in digital project planning, small-scale seed funding, scholarships and access to expert technologists who can develop prototypes and troubleshoot issues. We're proud to work with a range of researchers across disciplines to move their digital projects forward and turn ideas into realities.

PROJECTS

REGRESSION CHALLENGE APP

We helped Dr Glenna Nightingale develop 'Regression Challenge', a new app that will be used to teaching quantitative methods in Nursing. This project allowed Glenna to develop more challenges for the game, design the interface and interactive guide, and build a scoring mechanism so players can evaluate their learning. The app is openly accessible and will particularly support postgraduate students in the School of Health in Social Sciences.

THE JOURNEY OF THE VIRUS: A VR APPLICATION AND RESEARCH TOOL FOR CHILDREN

We supported Rea Michalopoulou's project to develop a VR app to use in schools as part of her research into the perception of Covid and other viruses. COVID-19 has led to a rapid and ever-changing public communication landscape, providing a unique opportunity to study lay people's understanding of the virus. Previous research on children's understanding of diseases is outdated, and it remains unclear how children conceptualise COVID-19 information. Rea created a prototype Virtual Reality (VR) application to collect data on how children understand infectious diseases, and to improve knowledge and understanding of COVID-19.

10

SANDPIT
APPLICATIONS

26

DATA
SURGERIES

3

IASH
FELLOWS

INCUBATING NEW IDEAS

We run regular open calls to invite researchers in the College of Arts, Humanities and Social Sciences to propose early stage projects that they'd like to explore with our research technologists. This year, ten applicants proposed ideas, and we were able to help them all take appropriate next steps. The projects that our team were able to support ranged from work on European politics, to video games, to mapping storytelling. This year, we were also delighted to support the development of research funding bids for two of the projects that came out of last year's sandpit.

RESEARCH DATA SURGERIES

Our team offers one-to-one advice to help troubleshoot and get researchers through tricky moments in their projects. This year we assisted 26 people with:

- multi-level, mixed and linear modelling
- merging and organising data
- web scraping and accessing social media data
- mapping geographic and network data
- visualisations

IASH FELLOWSHIPS 2023-24

We support outstanding digital scholars from around the world to visit Edinburgh through our partnership with the Institute for Advanced Studies in the Humanities.

Digital Scholarship Postdoctoral Fellow

DR SRUTHI HERBERT

Digitisation of Welfare and Implications for the Welfare State: An Examination through Social Welfare Funds in India.

Digital Scholarship Postdoctoral Fellow

DR SUZANNE BLACK

The Reviews Are In: A Computational Study of Fanfiction, Canonicity and Literary Value on Goodreads.

Digital Scholarship Visiting Fellow

DR MAYA DODD

Locating A New Historiography for India: Digital Archives and Public History.

COLLABORATION

WORKING WITH OTHERS.

Our partnerships and collaborations bring together a diversity of skills, perspectives and expertise to design, develop and deliver programmes. Through this collective effort, we build capacity for and explore issues around data-led and computational research. This year, we've worked with colleagues at the University and across the UK to offer opportunities for a variety of communities to learn about digital research and its contexts, from climate impacts to software engineering careers.

COLLABORATION

ACROSS THE COLLEGE OF ARTS, HUMANITIES AND SOCIAL SCIENCES

Growing Interest

TAILORED SUPPORT FOR LITERATURES, LANGUAGES AND CULTURES

We're working the School of Literatures, Languages and Cultures to increase awareness of and confidence in digital research methods. This year, we conducted a survey asking researchers in the School to reflect on their interest in digital research and the barriers they have experienced in uptaking new methods. Our findings led to us develop three bespoke sessions providing an introduction to thinking in terms of data and working with digitised texts.

Supporting Networks

DATA AND DIGITAL RESEARCH THEME

This year, we've been supporting the new leads of the Digital and Data research theme as they map, establish and highlight work across CAHSS. As they point out, the theme's research is crucial at a time when "the questions around digital and data are also broad public issues . . . of bias, discrimination, power, surveillance," which "the social sciences and the arts and humanities are actively answering."

Building Capacity

A DEEP DIVE INTO DIGITAL METHODS FOR HISTORY, CLASSICS AND ARCHAEOLOGY

Over the past five years, we have worked with the School of History, Classics and Archaeology to support their digital research community. As well as participating in welcome week this year, we provided their postgraduates with a deep dive into digital methods, showing them the kinds of research made possible with data-led and computational methods.

TEACHING PROGRAMMING TO NON-PROGRAMMERS: EDINBURGH WINTER SCHOOL 2024

This year, we worked with our colleagues Kasia Banas and Pawel Orzechowski from the Usher Institute to deliver a Winter School for methods in Teaching Programming to Non-Programmers. Sessions during the one-day event focused on pair and peer programming, code as peer assessment, teaching R, balancing theory with programming, and integrating pedagogy and practice. Olivia Guest and Sam Forbes delivered the event's keynote, 'Inclusivity in teaching programming'. Participants were keen to continue the conversation, which led to discussion of potential future activities and publications.

WORKSHOPS AND PEDAGOGY

We have continued to play a key role in the work of the Digital Humanities Climate Coalition (DHCC), a Community Interest Group of the UK-Ireland DH Association. Hosting monthly meetups, we have supported the growth of the DHCC community and shared the toolkit with new audiences. Our Director, Lisa Oty, delivered a keynote address at the University of Salford titled 'Parallel Paths: Supporting Open and Sustainable Research with the Digital Humanities Climate Coalition Toolkit', which focused on intersections between sustainability and open research. She also led a workshop at the UK-Ireland DH Association Conference at the University of Cork that focused on materials for teaching with the DHCC toolkit, an area which we hope to expand and grow over the coming year.

RSE SUMMER SCHOOL

The 2024 Digital Humanities & Research Software Engineering Summer School was hosted by CDCS in July, with invaluable funding support from The Alan Turing Institute and the Society of RSE. 22 attendees from Scotland, the rest of the UK, and even further afield gathered for four days of talks, discussions, workshops and social activities. The programme was aimed at people interested in a career in the growing field of RSE within the humanities and social sciences. Sessions were led by professionals working in RSE at universities around the UK. The first day was led by the Centre, with practical sessions focusing on principles of data visualisation using R and D3. The next day, Cambridge Digital Humanities presented a day of talks and activities about writing sustainable code. On day three, King's Digital Lab covered the challenges of digital creativity and creating impact while working effectively with collaborators and clients. The final day, the Alan Turing Institute focused on strategies for collaborating on code, highlighting Git as a key tool for doing so.

CREATIVE INFORMATICS BOOK LAUNCH

We were delighted to see the new volume Data-Driven Innovation in the Creative Industries come out in April. This book is the work of our collaborators at the Creative Informatics programme, a major investment from the AHRC which has delivered fantastic outcomes over the last five years. The book "examines how the creative industries can be best supported to make use of data-driven innovation and digital technology opportunities", sharing the insights and knowledge developed across the programme. The chapter on 'Digital and Data Literacy: models for data training and upskilling for the future creative industries' was co-authored by our CDCS Training Manager, Lucia Michielin.

INFRASTRUCTURE

BUILDING RESEARCH NETWORKS

No centre is an island, and we rely on a vast landscape of networks, tools, people and resources to deliver support to our community. Our work encompasses identifying, connecting to, supporting and sometimes developing effective digital research infrastructure. This year, we were delighted to begin working more closely with technical experts across EFI and CAHSS, pooling our knowledge and skills within the EFI Research Technology Service. We were also pleased to support the University of Edinburgh in becoming a member of DARIAH-EU, a major European network for digital research, and to continue our support of Programming Historian.

DARIAH DAY 2024

UNIVERSITY OF EDINBURGH BECOMES DARIAH COOPERATING PARTNER

In March 2024, the University of Edinburgh became a cooperating partner of DARIAH-EU, a European Research Infrastructure Consortium (ERIC) that empowers research communities with digital methods to create, connect and share knowledge. We're excited about the collaborative opportunities that membership brings, and we look forward to working more closely with other digital research hubs and centres of expertise across the UK and Europe. DARIAH membership also offers new opportunities for us to share our work via DARIAH-Campus, working groups and other initiatives in the coming years.

DARIAH DAY 2024

This year, we worked with the other UK cooperating partners (the Universities of Brighton, Exeter and Leeds; Kings College London and the School of Advanced Study, University of London) to programme and deliver UK DARIAH Day, held at the University of Leeds. The event brought together researchers and practitioners with an interest in Digital Humanities to consider opportunities and challenges around research infrastructures in the UK, showcase current tools and projects, and build national and regional networks. Highlights of the event included a keynote from Sally Chambers, Head of Research Infrastructures Services at The British Library and a director of DARIAH; a project showcase and collaboration catalyst; and an opportunity to discuss the UK's digital research landscape, including opportunities for enhancing infrastructure in the future.

GROWING TECHNICAL CAPACITY WITHIN EFI

We were delighted to welcome Dr Alexis Pister this year, who joined us as EFI's Data Visualisation Engineer. Alexis will be working within the EFI makerspace to support access to visualisation tools and software. He works with CDCS as part of the Research Technology Service, and engages with the VisHub research group based in Design Informatics.

SUPPORTING TRANSKRIBUS

We are founding members of the READ COOP, a purpose-driven co-operative, which supports the Transkribus platform for handwriting recognition. Transkribus is a valuable tool that enables researchers to digitise, analyse and publish historical documents. We support use of Transkribus for University of Edinburgh researchers, and can offer user seats, credits, guidance and support.

PROGRAMMING HISTORIAN

We are proud to be institutional partners of Programming Historian again this year. As gold-tier partners, we worked together on delivering masterclasses and silent discos. Programming Historian has now published over 250 digital humanities methods lessons online. Over the past 12 months, they have published a total of 23 new lessons, of which 13 are originals and 10 are translations.

DIGITAL RESEARCH PRIZES

RECOGNISING RESEARCH EXCELLENCE

Every year, we celebrate the amazing work of our community with our Digital Research Prizes. This year, we received nominations from a diverse range of fields including Law, Sociology, Economics, Education, Literature, Linguistics, Creative Arts and Politics. In June, we invited all of our nominees to a lunch reception in the newly opened EFI building, where they could mingle and read about one another's work on posters before the winning projects were announced. Congratulations, again, to all whose work was recognised!

BEST SMALL DATA-DRIVEN PROJECT

WINNER

SYSTEMIC STRUCTURE OF KINSHIP IS SHAPED BY EVOLUTIONARY PROCESSES

Maisy Hallam, Fiona Jordan, Simon Kirby and Kenny Smith

“Very interesting cross-cultural project combining social and linguistic evolution. Novel but understandable methodology was developed with clear visualisations.”

Highly Commended

Beyond ‘emergencies’? Reporting on humanitarian issues around the world

Kate Wright, Dani Madrid-Morales and Christopher Barrie

Highly Commended

Measuring the Rise and Fall of a Subreddit using Text Analytics: The Life Course of r/Antiwork

Ari Stillman

BEST DATASET

WINNER

BEYOND HUMANITARIAN ‘EMERGENCIES’

Kate Wright and Dani Madrid-Morales

“Not only adheres to FAIR principles with clear, transparent documentation, but also exemplifies how data-driven analysis can reshape disciplines by calling into question existing ideas. The dataset has relevance outside of the authors’ area of research and could, for instance, influence how (inter) national bodies respond to humanitarian issues or otherwise contribute to policy.”

“Very well commented and structured dataset that could be used besides the purpose of creation.”

“Very impressive capture of a decade of global media. Nicely documented with metadata and open license. I hope there will be a continuation of the collection over subsequent years.”

BEST IMPACT FROM A DATA-LED PROJECT

JOINT WINNER

GENDER-ING ELT: INTERNATIONAL PERSPECTIVES, PRACTICES, POLICIES

Vander Viana, Aisling O’Boyle (Northern Ireland), Danielle de Almeida Menezes (Brazil), Sibonile Edith Ellece (Botswana), Udi Samanhudi (Indonesia), Anna Chesnokova (Ukraine), Fatima Sadiqi (Morocco), Gina Lontoc (Philippines), Gulnahr Begum (Northern Ireland), Hang Nguyen (Vietnam), Teresita Sevilla (Colombia), Yan Wen (China), Anna Robinson-Pant (England), Gulsah Kutuk (England), Elmakki Amiri (Morocco), Florence Nwaefuna (Botswana), Haiqin Wu (China), Hannah-Gazelle Gabrielle Ponce (Philippines), Hesam Sadeghian (Colombia), Mariana Nunes Monteiro (Brazil), Nika Marushchak (Ukraine), Pamela Joy Mercado (Philippines), Rahmi Amalia (Indonesia), Ranjit Podder (Bangladesh), Tung Vu (Vietnam), and Via Allison Del Rosario (Philippines)

“A wide-ranging international impact that is positioned to make a significant contribution to addressing the gender gap in education, starting with ELT.”

“Excellent community engagement. Global impact and use.”

“Great project with worldwide influence.”

BEST IMPACT FROM A DATA-LED PROJECT

JOINT WINNER

THE INFLUENCE POLICING PROJECT

Ben Collier, James Stewart, Lydia Wilson, Daniel R Thomas and Shane Horgan

“Multi-institution project with strong international impact in the area of security and influence, along with considered use (pros and cons) of algorithmically-directed decision making and awareness of bias.”

“Very significant and impactful project.”

BEST NOVEL USE OF A DIGITAL METHOD

WINNER

NEWS MEDIA AS A LENS: EXPLORING NEIGHBOURHOOD HEALTH THROUGH THE ANALYSIS OF GEOPARSED AND CLUSTERED LOCAL NEWS

Eleojo Abubakar, Andreas Grivas, Claire Grover, Richard Tobin, Clare Llewellyn, Chunyu Zheng, Chris Dibben, Alan Marshall, Jamie Pearce, Beatrice Alex

“This interdisciplinary project itself makes a strong contribution to understanding community health in Scotland, and the success of the methodology suggests a wider application of this framework to assessing community health via local news in other areas. I especially appreciate the researchers’ testing of their methods to confirm that the correlation they had uncovered was, indeed, reliable!”

“Interesting approach that brings together different methodologies to analyse large datasets and rethink methodological questions.”

Highly Commended

Raw Green Rust - Antagonistic Sextet

Jules Rawlinson, Owen Green and Dave Murray-Rust

DATA

OUR YEAR IN NUMBERS

Our community is expanding and our online presence continues to grow. Our mailing list has reached a new milestone with over 2,000 subscribers, and our website and social media platforms are seeing increased activity, peaking at over 3,000 website visits in a single month. Here's how the analytics stack up.

AUDIENCE

- China 2.29%
- Germany 2.55%
- India 3.67%
- US 10.22%
- UK 53.57% (Edinburgh 21.16%)
- Other 27.7%

Breakdown of the top geographic locations of our web audience

WEBSITE

Recorded visits to the website, showing spikes of 1,100+ in November, January, April and May

VISITORS

Total number of visitors

Total number of page views

Unique visitors to website

Returning visitors to website (14%)

SOCIALS

+28K
IMPRESSIONS
PER MONTH

3.3%
ENGAGEMENT
RATE

BUDGET AUGUST 2023 / JULY 2024 BREAKDOWN

TOTAL SPEND £245.5K

- Staff £177.5K
- Events £9K
- Bursaries & Scholarships £13.4K
- Projects £5K
- Training £33.6K
- Other £7K

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